

Surface-induced formation of stereogenic centers on gold nanoparticles through diastereoselective interfacial Henry reaction: an NMR investigation

Gisya Abdi¹ and [Abdolhamid Alizadeh](#)^{1,2}

¹ Department of Organic Chemistry, Faculty of Chemistry, Razi University, Kermanshah 6714967346, Iran

² Nanoscience & Nanotechnology Research Center (NNRC), Razi University, Kermanshah 6714967346, Iran

Abstract

This study aims at the synthesis of gold nanoparticles (2–3 nm) functionalized with different nitroalkane-terminated thiols and investigates the chemical reactivity of these confined nitroalkanes towards aldehydes to yield β -nitroalcohols. Interfacial Henry reaction between fixed nitroalkane-terminated thiols with various aromatic and heteroaromatic aldehydes resulted in stereogenic centers on the surface of mixed-monolayer-protected gold nanoparticles (MMPNs). The ratio of the resulting diastereomers was determined by ¹H NMR spectroscopy. It was found that some parameters such as the chain length of nitroalkyl and the nature of aromatic aldehyde play the main role in affecting the diastereomeric ratio on the surface of MMPNs. Certain trends have been analyzed from the data, and it can be inferred that some aldehydes approximately prefer the formation of anti diastereomers as the predominant products, while others give syn β -nitroalcohols. We have attributed this stereoselectivity to the packed layers, forceful lateral interactions (van der Waals), and intramolecular hydrogen bonding on the surface of modified gold nanoparticles that are able to suppress the role of solvent and intermolecular interactions.

Keywords: Interfacial Henry reaction, Stereogenic centers, Gold nanoparticles.